

Teachers' Burnout and Students' Learning Outcomes in Mathematics

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Abstract. Teacher burnout has become a significant concern in education due to its potential impact on instructional quality and student learning outcomes. Although previous studies have examined burnout and academic achievement separately, limited empirical evidence exists on their relationship within mathematics education in localized school contexts. This study examined the relationship between teachers' burnout and students' performance in mathematics to provide empirical evidence for improving teacher well-being and student achievement. Specifically, it determined the extent of teacher burnout in terms of instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment; assessed students' performance using their Mean Percentage Score (MPS); and identified the significant relationship between the variables. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design and involved 30 mathematics teachers from Zamboanga City High School–Main. Data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire and official school records. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used, while Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was applied to test the relationship between variables. Results revealed that teachers experienced a very low extent of burnout across all dimensions, indicating minimal emotional exhaustion and effective management of instructional responsibilities. Students obtained a very satisfactory level of performance in mathematics, with a Mean Percentage Score of 89.90. Furthermore, Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between teacher burnout and student performance ($r = -0.368$, $p = 0.046$), indicating that higher levels of burnout were associated with lower student achievement in mathematics. Although the relationship was weak to moderate, it highlighted the importance of teacher well-being in influencing learning outcomes. The findings emphasized the need to sustain teacher support systems and wellness programs to maintain effective instruction and improve student achievement. Future research may explore additional factors such as student motivation, teaching strategies, and classroom environment to further explain variations in mathematics performance.

Keywords: Instructional Assessment; Instructional Delivery; Instructional Design; Learning Outcomes; Mathematics Performance; Mean Percentage Score; Teacher Burnout.

Introduction

Education played a vital role in national development, and teachers served as one of the most influential factors affecting students' academic achievement. In mathematics education, teachers performed essential instructional functions such as lesson planning, instructional delivery, classroom management, and assessment of learning. However, the increasing demands of the teaching profession often led to prolonged stress, which may result in teacher burnout. Teacher burnout was defined as a psychological syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment due to prolonged exposure to occupational stress (Maslach & Jackson, 1981).

This phenomenon was further explained by the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) theory, which posited that burnout occurred when job demands exceeded available resources, resulting in reduced energy and professional effectiveness (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). In educational settings, mathematics teachers were particularly vulnerable due to curriculum pressures, complex subject content, and students' varying levels of engagement. These conditions may affect the quality of instruction and ultimately influence students' academic performance.

Empirical studies have shown that teacher burnout was negatively associated with instructional quality and student achievement. For instance, Klusmann et al. (2016) found that teachers' emotional

exhaustion significantly predicted lower student performance in mathematics, while Madigan and Kim (2021) reported that teacher burnout was associated with reduced academic achievement and weaker student learning outcomes.

Despite the growing international literature on teacher burnout, a clear research gap remained in localized Philippine contexts, particularly in relation to how specific dimensions of burnout—such as instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment—were associated with students' mathematics performance in a single-school setting. Most existing studies focused on general teacher populations or broad academic outcomes, with limited emphasis on subject-specific and school-based analyses. This lack of localized evidence created a need to examine the phenomenon within specific educational environments to better understand its contextual effects.

In the Philippine setting, mathematics continued to be one of the core subjects where students often struggled, making teacher effectiveness highly critical in shaping learning outcomes. Therefore, examining the relationship between teacher burnout and students' mathematics performance provided valuable empirical evidence for improving instructional quality and teacher well-being.

This study aims to determine the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment. Furthermore, it seeks to determine the students' performance in mathematics and identify whether a significant relationship exists between teachers' burnout and students' learning outcomes. The findings of this study may provide insights for school administrators, teachers, and policymakers in developing programs and interventions that promote teachers' well-being and improve students' academic achievement.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the following:

1. What is the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of:
 - 1.1 Instructional Design;
 - 1.2 Instructional Delivery; and
 - 1.3 Instructional Assessment?
2. What is the students performance in mathematics?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers burnout in teaching mathematics and students performance?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focuses on determining the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment. It also examines the students' performance in mathematics and the significant relationship between teacher burnout and students' learning outcomes. The respondents of the study include 30 mathematics teachers of Zamboanga City High School - Main in Zamboanga City Division during the School Year 2025–2026. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. Data regarding teacher burnout gathered through a researcher-made questionnaire, while students' mathematics performance is based on their grades or assessment results. The study is limited only to the identified variables and respondents included in the research locale. Other factors affecting students' performance such as socioeconomic status, parental involvement, learning resources, and students' attitudes toward mathematics are not included in the study.

Literature Review

Teacher Burnout

Teacher burnout refers to a psychological syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment resulting from prolonged exposure to work-related stress (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). It is widely understood through the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) theory, which explains that burnout develops when job demands exceed available resources, leading to energy depletion and reduced professional functioning (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Teaching is considered one of the most emotionally demanding professions due to workload, classroom management, and student-related pressures (Chang, 2009). Empirical research has consistently shown that teacher burnout negatively affects instructional quality and student outcomes. For example, Madigan and Kim (2021) found through a systematic review that teacher burnout is associated with lower academic achievement and reduced student motivation. Similarly, Klusmann et al. (2016) demonstrated that teachers' emotional exhaustion significantly predicts lower student performance in mathematics, even after controlling for classroom and teacher characteristics. However, studies also suggest that the strength of this relationship may vary depending on

school context and instructional support systems, indicating that burnout does not affect all teachers and learners equally.

Instructional Design

Instructional design refers to the systematic planning and structuring of lessons, learning activities, and assessments to achieve specific learning outcomes. It is grounded in instructional systems theory, which emphasizes alignment between objectives, teaching strategies, and evaluation methods (Reigeluth, 2013). Research indicates that effective instructional design improves student understanding and achievement by organizing content in a meaningful and developmentally appropriate sequence (Branch, 2018). In mathematics education, structured instructional planning is particularly important due to the abstract and cumulative nature of mathematical concepts (Hill et al., 2019). However, theoretical models such as the JD-R framework suggest that teacher burnout may reduce cognitive resources needed for effective planning, potentially affecting lesson quality (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Despite this, some findings indicate that experienced teachers may maintain instructional planning quality through established routines, suggesting that the effect of burnout on instructional design may not always be direct or uniform.

Instructional Delivery

Instructional delivery refers to how teachers implement lesson plans in the classroom, including communication, engagement strategies, and interaction with students. According to Hattie (2009), instructional quality is one of the strongest predictors of student achievement, emphasizing the importance of effective teaching delivery. Research shows that teacher behavior during instruction strongly influences student engagement and learning outcomes. Klusmann et al. (2016) found that teachers' emotional exhaustion is negatively associated with students' mathematics achievement, partly due to reduced instructional support and classroom organization. Similarly, Madigan and Kim (2021) reported that burnout is linked to lower-quality instructional interactions. However, other studies suggest that the relationship between burnout and instructional delivery may be moderated by school support systems, teacher experience, and classroom environment, indicating variability in outcomes across contexts.

Instructional Assessment

Instructional assessment involves the use of tests, quizzes, assignments, and performance tasks to evaluate student learning and inform instruction. Effective assessment practices are essential for improving student achievement through feedback and instructional adjustment (Black & William, 2009). Brookhart (2017) emphasized that well-designed assessment practices improve student understanding by guiding learning and identifying areas for improvement. In mathematics education, assessment is critical for evaluating problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding. However, research suggests that teacher burnout may reduce the effectiveness of assessment practices by limiting timely feedback and increasing workload pressure (Madigan & Kim, 2021). Despite this, standardized school assessment systems may reduce variability in grading practices, meaning the impact of burnout on assessment quality may depend on institutional structures.

Students' Performance in Mathematics

Students' performance in mathematics refers to learners' achievement as measured through grades, test scores, or standardized assessments. It reflects conceptual understanding, problem-solving ability, and application of mathematical knowledge. Research consistently identifies teacher effectiveness as a key predictor of student achievement. Wayne and Youngs (2003) found that teacher characteristics significantly influence student learning gains. Additionally, Klusmann et al. (2016) demonstrated that teacher emotional exhaustion negatively affects student mathematics achievement, highlighting the importance of teacher well-being. However, student performance is also influenced by other factors such as prior knowledge, motivation, and classroom environment, suggesting that academic achievement is a multi-determined outcome rather than being solely dependent on teacher-related variables. The reviewed literature consistently indicates that teacher burnout is a multidimensional construct that negatively affects instructional processes, including instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment. Across studies, there is strong agreement that burnout reduces teacher effectiveness, particularly through emotional exhaustion that limits instructional engagement and classroom support (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017; Madigan & Kim, 2021). Empirical findings further demonstrate that teacher burnout is significantly associated with lower student achievement, especially in mathematics education (Klusmann et al., 2016). However, existing research also highlights variability in findings, suggesting that the impact of burnout may be moderated by contextual factors such as school support systems, teacher experience, and classroom environment. Similarly, while instructional quality is consistently linked to student performance (Hattie, 2009; Wayne & Youngs, 2003),

studies emphasize that learning outcomes are also influenced by student-related and environmental factors. Despite extensive international research, there remains a need for localized studies examining how teacher burnout relates specifically to mathematics performance in Philippine school contexts. This gap supports the present study, which investigates the relationship between teacher burnout and students' mathematics performance in a localized setting.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment, as well as to examine the relationship between teachers' burnout and students' learning outcomes in mathematics. A descriptive-correlational design is a quantitative research approach that describes variables and determines the degree of relationship between them without manipulating any variables involved. According to Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018), correlational research is used to examine relationships among variables in educational settings through statistical analysis. This design was appropriate for the study because it allowed the researcher to gather quantitative data regarding teachers' burnout and students' performance in mathematics and to determine whether a significant relationship existed between these variables. Specifically, it described the extent of burnout experienced by mathematics teachers and the level of students' performance based on their Mean Percentage Score (MPS). Furthermore, the design was suitable because it did not seek to establish cause-and-effect relationships but rather focused on identifying significant associations between variables using appropriate statistical tools.

Sampling Design

The study employed a stratified random sampling technique to ensure that Mathematics teachers were adequately represented across different grade levels within Zamboanga City High School–Main. The population of Mathematics teachers was first grouped into strata based on their teaching assignment or grade level. From each stratum, participants were randomly selected to ensure equal representation and reduce sampling bias. The sample size consisted of 30 Mathematics teachers, determined using Slovin's formula at a specified margin of error. This sampling procedure ensured that each teacher had an equal opportunity to be included in the study, thereby increasing the reliability and generalizability of the findings within the school context.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Zamboanga City High School–Main, which has approximately 42 Mathematics teachers among a total of 292 faculty members. The school was selected due to the presence of Mathematics teachers handling diverse workloads, student populations, and instructional responsibilities, making it suitable for examining teacher burnout and students' learning outcomes.

Research Participants

The participants of the study were 30 Mathematics teachers currently employed at Zamboanga City High School–Main. These teachers were selected as primary respondents because they were directly involved in classroom instruction and were most exposed to workload demands associated with teaching Mathematics. As evidenced by Klusmann et al. (2016), teacher emotional exhaustion has measurable effects on students' academic achievement, particularly in mathematics.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a researcher-made questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. The instrument was designed to determine the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment. It consisted of 15 indicators, with 5 items for each dimension. The instrument used a four-point Likert scale with the following responses: 4 – Always, 3 – Often, 2 – Rarely, and 1 – Never. Students' performance in mathematics was measured using their Mean Percentage Score (MPS) obtained from quarterly examinations, summative assessments, or official school records. To ensure the validity of the instrument, it was submitted for content validation by two (2) experts holding Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degrees in the field of education and research methodology. Their feedback was used to refine and improve the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the questionnaire items. In addition, a pilot testing was conducted with a group of respondents who were not part of the actual sample to determine the reliability of the instrument. The

reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, and the results indicated acceptable internal consistency for all constructs.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first sought permission from the school principal of Zamboanga City High School–Main through a formal letter of request explaining the purpose and objectives of the study. Upon approval, coordination was made with school heads and Mathematics department coordinators to facilitate proper scheduling and distribution of the questionnaire. After securing permission, the researcher personally distributed the Google Form link containing the questionnaire to the respondents. Prior to answering, the participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and the assurance of confidentiality of their responses, which were used solely for academic purposes. The respondents were given sufficient time to accomplish the questionnaire to ensure accuracy and honesty in their responses. After retrieval, all collected data were checked for completeness, encoded, and prepared for statistical analysis. The results were then interpreted in relation to the study's objectives. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of teachers' burnout and the level of students' performance in mathematics. To interpret the mean scores, a Likert scale interpretation was applied. To determine the significant relationship between teachers' burnout and students' performance, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used. The level of significance was set at 0.05 alpha level. All statistical computations were processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of Instructional Design, Instructional Delivery, and Instructional Assessment?

Table 1. Extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of Instructional Design.

	Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.	I feel mentally exhausted when preparing mathematics lesson plans.	1.36	Never	Very Low Extent
2.	I feel overwhelmed by curriculum requirements in mathematics teaching.	1.36	Never	Very Low Extent
3.	I feel pressured in aligning mathematics lessons with learning competencies.	1.33	Never	Very Low Extent
4.	I experience stress in preparing classroom learning resources in mathematics.	1.36	Never	Very Low Extent
5.	I find lesson planning in mathematics emotionally draining.	1.4	Never	Very Low Extent
	Over-all Mean	1.37	Never	Very Low Extent

The results in Table 1 presented the level of teacher burnout in terms of instructional design in mathematics teaching. The highest mean was found in statement 5 ($M=1.40$), indicating that lesson planning was the most challenging aspect, although still at a very low extent. The lowest mean was observed in statement 3 ($M=1.33$), suggesting minimal perceived pressure in curriculum alignment. The overall mean of 1.37 reflected a Very Low Extent of burnout in instructional design. This implied that teachers generally did not experience significant exhaustion or stress in preparing mathematics lessons. This finding was consistent with Maslach and Jackson (1981), who described burnout as emotional exhaustion and reduced personal accomplishment, which appeared minimally present in this dimension. Similarly, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2011) emphasized that teacher burnout is strongly linked to workload and role conflict, which appeared low in the present context.

Table 2. Extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of Instructional Delivery.

	Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.	I feel emotionally exhausted while teaching mathematics lessons.	1.43	Never	Very Low Extent
2.	I experience difficulty maintaining students' attention during mathematics discussions.	1.23	Never	Very Low Extent
3.	I experience stress in managing classroom behavior during mathematics classes.	1.26	Never	Very Low Extent
4.	I experience frustration when students fail to understand mathematics lessons.	1.23	Never	Very Low Extent
5.	I become impatient when students struggle with mathematics activities.	1.56	Never	Very Low Extent
	Over-all Mean	1.35	Never	Very Low Extent

Table 2 showed the level of burnout in instructional delivery during mathematics teaching. The highest mean was reflected in statement 5 ($M=1.56$), suggesting that emotional response toward student difficulty was the most noticeable aspect, although still at a very low level. The lowest means were found in statements 2 and 4 ($M=1.23$), indicating very minimal difficulty in classroom engagement and emotional frustration. The overall mean of 1.35 indicated a Very Low Extent of burnout in instructional delivery. This result implied that teachers were generally able to manage classroom instruction effectively without significant emotional exhaustion. According to Chang (2009), burnout in instructional interactions is often driven by classroom management stress and student misbehavior; however, such stressors were not strongly evident in this study. Aloe, Shisler, and Norris (2014) further noted that classroom disruptions are major predictors of burnout, which appeared minimal among respondents.

Table 3. Extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics in terms of Instructional Assessment

	Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.	I experience difficulty checking students' mathematics outputs on time.	1.33	Never	Very Low Extent
2.	I feel overwhelmed by the number of mathematics assessments to prepare.	1.26	Never	Very Low Extent
3.	I feel stressed in giving feedback to students in mathematics.	1.26	Never	Very Low Extent
4.	I find assessment tasks in mathematics stressful.	1.3	Never	Very Low Extent
5.	I experience stress in analyzing students' mathematics test results.	1.63	Never	Very Low Extent
	Over-all Mean	1.36	Never	Very Low Extent

Table 3 presented the level of teacher burnout in instructional assessment in mathematics. The highest mean was observed in statement 5 ($M=1.63$), indicating that data interpretation and evaluation of student performance was the most stressful aspect, although still at a very low level. The lowest means were found in statements 2 and 3 ($M=1.26$), suggesting minimal workload-related and feedback-related stress. The overall mean of 1.36 reflected a Very Low Extent of burnout in instructional assessment. This suggested that teachers were generally not overwhelmed by assessment-related tasks. Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2016) noted that assessment and grading responsibilities may contribute to emotional exhaustion when workload increases; however, this was not strongly observed in the present study. Maslach, Schaufeli, and Leiter (2001) emphasized that burnout emerges when demands exceed resources, which appeared minimal in this context.

Table 4. Summary of the extent of teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics.

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Instructional Design	1.36	Very Low Extent
Instructional Delivery	1.35	Very Low Extent
Instructional Assessment	1.36	Very Low Extent
Over-All Mean	1.36	Very Low Extent

Table 4 summarized the overall extent of teacher burnout, revealing that mathematics teachers experienced a Very Low Extent of burnout in instructional design ($M=1.37$), instructional delivery ($M=1.35$), and instructional assessment ($M=1.36$), with an overall mean of 1.36. This indicates that respondents rarely experienced exhaustion, stress, or reduced effectiveness in instructional responsibilities. The result suggests that teachers were still capable of performing instructional tasks effectively despite professional demands.

This finding aligns with studies suggesting that teacher well-being enhances instructional quality and engagement (Madigan & Kim, 2021). The consistently low burnout levels further imply stable teaching conditions within the setting.

Research Question 2: What is the students' performance in mathematics?

Table 5. Students' performance in mathematics

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
Students' performance in mathematics (Mean Percentage Score)	89.90	Very Satisfactory

Table 5 showed that students obtained a Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 89.90, interpreted as Very Satisfactory performance. This indicates that students demonstrated a high level of achievement in mathematics and were able to meet expected learning competencies. The result suggests adequate conceptual understanding and skill development, possibly influenced by effective instructional practices and supportive learning environments. Wayne and Youngs (2003) emphasized that teacher effectiveness significantly contributes to student achievement. In this study, high performance may reflect strong instructional delivery and consistent academic support.

Research Question 3: Is there a significant relationship between teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics and students' performance?

Table 6. Relationship between teachers' burnout in teaching mathematics and students' performance

Variables		r - value	p - value	Interpretation
x	y			
Teachers' Burnouts	Students Performance	-.368	.046	Significant

In Table 6, Pearson correlation analysis revealed a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.368$ with a p-value of 0.046, indicating a statistically Significant Relationship between teacher burnout and students' performance at the 0.05 level. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. The negative correlation indicated an inverse relationship, meaning that as teacher burnout increased, student performance tended to decrease. In terms of effect size interpretation, the correlation coefficient of -0.368 indicated a weak to moderate negative relationship, based on commonly used guidelines (Cohen, 1988). Practically, this suggests that while burnout was not the sole determinant of student performance, it still had a meaningful influence on learning outcomes. The result indicates that higher levels of teacher burnout are associated with lower student performance. These findings were consistent with Klusmann et al. (2016), who found that teacher emotional exhaustion negatively affected student mathematics achievement, and Madigan and Kim (2021), who reported that teacher burnout is associated with lower academic performance. Overall, the results highlight that maintaining teacher well-being is important not only statistically but also practically in sustaining student success in mathematics.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants. Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained from the school administration and relevant authorities of the identified research locale. Ethical clearance was obtained through institutional administrative approval in accordance with school research guidelines. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, the nature of their participation, and their right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty or negative consequences. Informed consent was secured prior to data collection to ensure participants' awareness and agreement. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the research process. No names or identifying information of teachers or students were disclosed in any part of the study, and all collected data were encoded and used solely for academic and research purposes. Data were stored securely and accessed only by the researcher. The ethical procedures followed in this study were guided by the core principles of research ethics, including respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, as emphasized by the American Psychological Association (APA, 2020).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that mathematics teachers experienced a very low extent of burnout in terms of instructional design, instructional delivery, and instructional assessment. This indicates that the respondents were generally able to manage their teaching responsibilities effectively without significant emotional exhaustion or work-related stress. The result aligns with the conceptualization of burnout as emotional exhaustion and reduced professional efficacy (Maslach & Jackson, 1981) and supports the idea that manageable instructional demands and adequate working conditions contribute to reduced burnout levels (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011; Maslach et al., 2001). In addition, students obtained a very satisfactory Mean Percentage Score (MPS), which suggests strong academic performance in mathematics and may reflect effective instructional practices and conducive learning environments (Wayne & Youngs, 2003). Furthermore, the study revealed a significant negative relationship between teachers' burnout and students' performance in mathematics, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding implies that increases in teacher burnout are associated with decreases in student performance, while lower burnout levels correspond to higher academic achievement. Although the relationship was weak to moderate in strength, it highlights the critical role of teacher well-being in influencing student learning outcomes. This result is consistent with prior studies indicating that teacher emotional exhaustion negatively affects student achievement and instructional quality (Klusmann et al., 2016; Madigan & Kim, 2021). Importantly, the study contributes to mathematics education by providing context-specific empirical evidence on the linkage between teacher burnout and student achievement within a Philippine school setting. It reinforces the understanding that teacher well-being is not only a professional concern but also a determinant of student success in mathematics. For educational research, the study adds to the growing body of literature supporting the Job Demands–Resources perspective by demonstrating how instructional-related stressors indirectly relate to learner outcomes. Practically, the findings provide a basis for school administrators and policymakers to design targeted interventions that promote teacher wellness, reduce instructional stress, and sustain high-quality mathematics instruction. Thus, the study bridges a gap between teacher psychology and student academic performance in mathematics education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that school administrators and educational leaders continue to strengthen and expand existing Department of Education (DepEd) teacher well-being and mental health programs to sustain the very low level of burnout among mathematics teachers. Existing initiatives may be enhanced by providing more regular mental health check-ins, strengthening peer support and mentoring activities, improving workload management strategies, and increasing access to stress management and wellness activities tailored to teachers' instructional responsibilities. In addition, schools may further improve existing teacher wellness monitoring mechanisms by regularly assessing teacher workload and emotional well-being to identify potential concerns at an early stage. These interventions are consistent with the view of Maslach and Leiter (2016), who emphasized that organizational support is essential in preventing burnout and sustaining teacher engagement. It is also recommended that mathematics teachers continue to participate in and maximize existing professional development programs offered by DepEd and other educational institutions, particularly those focusing on lesson planning, differentiated instruction, and formative assessment strategies. Schools may further expand peer mentoring, instructional coaching, and Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) to encourage collaboration and the sharing of effective teaching practices. Since student performance was found to be very satisfactory, sustaining and enhancing instructional quality through these existing support systems may help maintain positive learning outcomes. As emphasized by Hattie (2009), teacher effectiveness remains one of the strongest determinants of student achievement. Furthermore, it is recommended that future researchers conduct expanded studies using mixed-method or longitudinal research designs to gain deeper insights into the relationship between teacher burnout and student performance over time. Future investigations may also include additional variables such as student motivation, classroom environment, teaching strategies, parental involvement, school leadership support, and access to learning resources to develop a more comprehensive understanding of factors influencing mathematics achievement. Madigan and Kim (2021) emphasized that multi-factorial approaches are necessary to better explain variations in student outcomes and teacher well-being across different educational contexts.

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